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SUCCESSFUL EXPERIENCE OF THE DECANTER CENTRIFUGE APPLICATION AT THE STAGE OF MECHANICAL DEWATERING IN COMMERCIAL LIGNIN PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY

Eduard Khamitov

lead application engineer,

member of the The Institution of Engineering and Technology (The IET)

Abstract

The time has come for real steps aimed at combating the global challenges faced by mankind, the main ones, according to the author, are warming and waste. At the interstate level, the leading countries have planned specific solutions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and waste disposal. In 2020, Glasgow hosted the World Climate Change Summit, during which more than thirty countries and six leading car manufacturers announced plans to phase out internal combustion engines by 2040. Almost every inhabitant of the globe saw or felt the melting of glaciers and objective warming. Warming and waste are two interrelated problems in human life. The implementation of the decisions taken will require years and huge financial investments. Therefore, the development of modern technologies for waste processing should be dealt with now. According to one study, South Korea recycles 49% of municipal solid waste. Sweden even makes money on waste disposal by importing it from neighboring countries. First, sorting is done for reuse, and everything that remains is burned. More than half of the energy for heating comes from burning garbage. But this applies mainly to solid household waste. Disposal of industrial waste is sometimes quite a difficult task and requires the use of the latest achievements in science and technology. The article is devoted to the optimization of one of the technological stages of industrial waste disposal, namely the mechanical dehydration of hydrolytic lignin. The author comes to the conclusion that, due to its physical properties, applicable dehydration of lignin is possible only with the help of centrifugation. The author seeks to analyze the process of separation of an aqueous suspension of lignin at different concentrations. Depending on what target product you plan to get from lignin, various technological operations will be selected accordingly. According to the author, in most lignin processing technologies, dehydration will be important and will determine the profitability of the entire technological process.

Keywords: lignin, lignosulfonates, carbon adsorbents, centrifugation, decantation, dewatering.

The environmentally friendly aspect of production is becoming increasingly important every day. Requirements for non-waste, minimal impact on the environment, and the so-called carbon footprint are becoming priorities and paramount. But this applies not only to modern production but also to the legacy inherited from outdated and sometimes closed enterprises, which left behind waste that still remains undisposed of. Often, waste from one production is the raw material for another production, subject to the availability of appropriate technologies. One of these resources is waste from the pulp, paper, and hydrolysis industries in the CIS countries. The amount of such waste is measured in millions of tons. This waste occupies large areas in the form of dumps and in municipal solid waste landfills, poses a danger to the environment and causes obvious harm to nature on the one hand, but can and already has industrial application somewhere on the other. This waste, like all others in principle, must be disposed of in a way that benefits the economy. The benefits for society and the biosphere are obvious. The main waste from hydrolysis production is powdered or hydrolyzed lignin and lignosulfonate, depending on what technology is used in production. The lignin content in wood ranges from 14 to 50% by weight, depending on the type and growing conditions of the trees; its content is higher in coniferous species than in deciduous ones [1]. There are two main pulping technologies, the most common being kraft pulping (in alkali) and the less commonly used sulphite pulping (in acid). Lignin obtained in sulfate production is sulfate lignin and is usually utilized in power plants for pulp and paper mills. During sulfite production, solutions of sulfite lignins (lignosulfonates)

are formed, some of which accumulate in lignin storages [2].

The range of potential and actual applications of sulfite lignins is quite wide. Due to its high caloric content, it is used as fuel. Through chemical and thermal treatment, lignin is given a porous structure. Due to its unique porous structure and physicochemical properties, lignin is actively used as an adsorbent in technological processes for environmental protection, including the cleanup of oil spills. Just as an adsorbent, lignin is actively used for medical purposes. In large quantities, modified hydrolytic lignins are widely used in metallurgy as reducing agents instead of coal and graphite. By oxidizing hydrolytic lignin, lignin reagents (nitrolignin) are obtained to reduce the viscosity and static shear stress of drilling fluids. The description of all possible products from lignin will take a lot of time, so I will briefly give a list that can hardly be called complete:

- **nitrolignin** for liquefying clay solutions in the oil industry instead of expensive drugs;
- **chlorolignin** for the precipitation of rare metals in solutions;
- **synthetic resins**, where a third of phenol is replaced by hydrolytic lignin;
- **resins** for preparing pulverbakelite, from which molds for cork casting are made; activated lignin as an enhancer of synthetic rubbers (lignin-pollen rubber is cheaper and 8–10 times stronger than unfilled rubber);
- **thermally insulating ligno-fiber boards** as a convenient and cheap building material, and much more, fuel briquettes, including those mixed with sawdust, coal, and peat dust;
- **fuel gas**, including with the generation of electricity in gas piston gas generators;
- **boiler fuel**;
- **reducing agents** for metals and silicon;
- **coals**, including activated ones;
- **sorbents** for cleaning urban and industrial wastewater;
- **sorbents** for spilled oil products;
- **sorbents** for heavy metals;
- **technological sorbents**;
- **oil sorbents**, materials used to collect oil and oil products from the surface of water bodies;
- **enterosorbents** for medical and veterinary purposes;
- **blowing agent** in the production of bricks and other ceramic products;
- **filler** for plastics and composite materials;
- **binder** for composite materials;
- **organic and organomineral fertilizers**, texture formers for natural and artificial soils, herbicides for the cultivation of certain crops (legumes);
- **raw materials** for the production of phenol, acetic, and oxalic acids;
- **additive** to asphalt concrete (preparation of lignin-bitumen mixtures, etc.).

The ash content of hydrolyzed lignin on a dry weight basis is 4.70%. The chemical composition of hydrolytic lignin largely depends on the nature and composition of the raw material, the hydrolysis regime, and other factors: lignin (40–88%), polysaccharides (13–45%), monosaccharides (1–3%), and substances of the lignohumic complex (2.5–5%), resinous (5–19%), ash (0.5–10%) substances, sulfuric and organic acids (0.4–4.6%) [3]. In the production of lignin-based sorbents, various options for activating the porous structure are used - chemical, thermal, or thermochemical. Dehydration is an intermediate operation and can be used in different technological processes. Both after neutralization and before drying [4]. The purpose of this work is to develop the technological and technical parameters of the mechanical dehydration of lignin. Centrifugal separation is currently the most effective technology for two-, three-, and sometimes four-phase separation [5]. This article presents and analyzes the results of pilot industrial tests of the use of industrial centrifuges with a solid wall and screw unloading of the solid phase (decanter). A description of the decanter centrifuge and a sketch are presented below to help understand the features of this dehydration technology.

Pic 1. Decanter diagram

During pilot-scale testing, dewatering was carried out using a decanter centrifuge with a dual-motor drive (Pic 1). This type of drive allows you to control the speed of the drum and auger independently through a variable-frequency drive (VFD). The speed of the drum and auger electric motors is constantly monitored and can be changed independently of each other. The speed of the drum creates a centrifugal field for the suspension, and the speed of the screw ensures the removal of the settled solid phase and its moisture content (the angle of the cone part, where drying occurs, is not calculated here). The frequency inverter not only provides the specified rotation speed but also controls the torque and temperature conditions of the electric motors. Overall, this ensures the efficiency, reliability, and safety of the decanter centrifuge. If the controlled parameters go beyond the setpoints, it leads to a transition to correction mode or an emergency stop. The normal operation of a decanter centrifuge is almost always automatic. This guarantees maximum hydration and safety at all times. The key parameter during operation is the torque on the auger. This is an indicator of the filling of the drum with solid phase, and, depending on this, the speed of the screw changes in one direction or another. Unlike other dewatering technologies, the decanter centrifuge operates continuously.

A screw pump must be used to feed the suspension into the decanter. This type of pump is most suitable for the requirements of automatic operation of a centrifuge — the ability to pump products with a high solids content and a direct dependence of performance on the drive speed. The change in pump performance also occurs due to a frequency-controlled drive, and it does not practically depend on the viscosity or percentage of the solid phase of the pumped product. Theoretically, the settling rate of a particle in a field of centrifugal forces is calculated using the Stokes formula.

$$Vg = \frac{d^2 * (\Delta\rho) * r\omega^2 (1)}{18 * \eta}$$

d particle diameter. The larger the diameter, the higher the rate of particle deposition.

ω angular rotation speed.

r radius of the particle's position from the axis of rotation.

$\Delta\rho$ the difference in densities between particles and liquids; the greater the difference in densities between particles and liquids, the higher the settling rate.

η dynamic viscosity of the liquid phase; the lower the dynamic viscosity of the product, the higher the rate of particle sedimentation.

The actual speed will naturally be lower. To understand the possibility of dehydration of an aqueous suspension of lignin, spin tests were carried out on a Specro laboratory centrifuge. This test is used to evaluate the suitability of centrifugation for a particular sample, since the process of measuring the densities of liquid and solid phases in a suspension is sometimes problematic and can take some time. If sedimentation of the solid phase occurs within 2-3 minutes and at a test tube rotation speed of 2000–3000 rpm, then there is a high probability that when using a decanter, separation will

also occur effectively. The laboratory centrifuge in this case is a model of a decanter centrifuge. The time limit of 2-3 minutes is explained by the fact that the residence time of the product in the decanter is precisely within these limits, and if sedimentation of the sample has not occurred during this time, then there is no point in organizing full-scale tests. The process of conducting pilot industrial tests is quite an expensive and time-consuming one.

Pic 2. Laboratory centrifuge

Separation efficiency is usually carried out by measuring the moisture content of the dewatered solids. The moisture content of the solid phase after dehydration depends on the nature of the product and the ability to remove the liquid phase from it. For manufacturers and suppliers of decanters, the moisture content of the solid phase (cake), along with performance, is fixed in the contract and measured during acceptance tests. Humidity during testing was measured using the Sartorius device (Pic 3).

Pic 3. Humidity meter

The particle size distribution (not consistent between batches) is given in Table 1.

Batch	Row lignin grading			
	20-45, μm	45-63, μm	63-125, μm	>125, μm
1	3,58%	39%	16,5%	40,9%
2	74,6%	7,35%	11,5%	5,55%
3	54%	8,2%	20,2%	17,6%

The pH value of the suspension was 6.31 (shown in Pic 4).

Pic 4. pH meter

The density of the suspension at a temperature of 20 °C was 1055 kg/m³ (Pic 5).

Pic 5. Density meter

Four samples of the suspension were preliminarily prepared with a lignin mass content of 10%, 15%, 20% and 25%. The results of centrifugation in a laboratory centrifuge are given in Table 2.

Table 2

Centrifugation time and results

Time	10% DS	15% DS	20% DS	25% DS
2 min.				
3 min.				

The technological scheme for testing is shown in Pic 6. Water in this scheme is, in principle, always necessary for washing the centrifuge after stopping or for additional dilution of the initial suspension.

Pic 6. Technological diagram

During the work, the main parameters were recorded, since there was no experience in dehydrating a lignin suspension. The moisture content of the suspension was measured before entering the decanter, and the moisture content of dehydrated lignin was measured at the outlet of the decanter.

Dehydrated lignin was the target product, and it was necessary to achieve its minimum moisture content. Due to the fact that the sedimentation rate is directly proportional to the size of the particles in the suspension, the smaller the particle size, the slower the sedimentation occurs. Therefore, treatment plants use special reagents called flocculants, which bind particles to each other in flocs to increase the retention coefficient. In this case, the use of flocculants is not acceptable since the target product, lignin, would lose its purity. Therefore, the productivity of the decanter will be less, and the time the lignin remains in the field of centrifugal forces should be increased. This is achieved by reducing the feed.

After the decanter reached a stable operating mode, sampling and humidity measurements were periodically carried out. The results are listed in Table 3.

Table 3

Dewatering results

Sample no.	Suspension humidity, %	Cake moisture, %	Humidity of centrate, %
1	80,20	63,82	99,82
2	79,66	61,30	99,54
3	80,10	59,33	99,81
4	80,80	64,07	99,98
5	78,90	64,00	99,67
6	79,60	64,16	99,84
7	78,60	61,67	99,91

Pic 7 shows the suspension at the decanter inlet, the dehydrated lignin (cake), and the filtrate (liquid phase). The consistency of the suspension at the inlet is homogeneous and pasty. Dehydrated lignin holds its shape well. The filtrate is quite turbid due to the presence of a fine lignin fraction.

Pic 7. Feed suspension, cake and filtrat

The mass balance of the dehydration process is given in Table 4.

Table 4

Dependence of the humidity of the lignin suspension and its volume

DS concentration in the initial suspension, %	Suspension volume at inlet, m ³ /h	Lignin concentration after dehydration, %	Volume of lignin after dehydration, m ³ /h
20	1	60	0,33

It turns out that by increasing the lignin concentration in the suspension twice, the volume of the lignin suspension decreases three times. From this, we see that the volume of lignin for the next drying stage is reduced by three times. Due to this, the energy costs for further drying are reduced significantly since the required moisture content of commercial lignin lies in the range of 10–16%. Energy costs of enterprises are one of the important indicators of profitability and determine whether the products produced will be competitive in the market. Due to the fact that the lignin fraction size is less than 1 mm, the use of other technologies, such as filtration, is hardly applicable. From experience, I can say that the initial suspension concentration of 20% DS is high enough for centrifugal separation. There is a very high probability that the retention coefficient and productivity will be higher with an initial concentration of lignin in the suspension of up to 10% DS. But unfortunately, it was not possible to check the separation at such a concentration due to time constraints. But this feature of centrifugal separation—that a high content of solids at the inlet often only worsens the separation — will be necessary during further operation. When organizing and designing a technological process, it is important to keep in mind that the pH of the suspension must be neutral. Otherwise, the cost of the decanter will be significantly higher since acid-resistant alloys are quite expensive.

To obtain a stable separation process, it is necessary to ensure the homogeneity of the suspension at the entrance to the decanter. For this, it is recommended to use mixers; in the absence of mixers, a recirculation pump can be used, but its efficiency is lower. To complete the production line, the type of feed pump must be an eccentric screw. Now this type of pump is considered standard due to such advantages as high efficiency, low specific energy consumption, high reliability, and the ability to pump media with a high solids content. The same pump can also be used to transport dehydrated lignin through a pipe. This delivery has proven itself well and has a number of advantages, including the compactness of the overall system for removing the dehydrated product, the absence of evaporation on the premises, and simpler and cheaper service. This study showed that the efficiency of lignin dehydration from an aqueous suspension is quite high and should be recommended for industrial use.

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